

Assessing the Effects of the Taxation System on Business Decisions in Zambia: A Case Study of Lusaka Central Business District (CBD) SMEs

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 30th Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: SMEs Taxation Business Decisions Tax Compliance Zambia</p>	<p>This study explored the impact of the system of taxation on business decisions among SMEs in Lusaka Central Business District, Zambia. The objective of this research was to establish the extent to which the taxation system in Zambia affects the decision-making of SME businesses regarding compliance behavior, the use of tax advisory services, and the impact of taxation on strategic business decisions. It had three objectives: assessing the level of tax compliance among SMEs in the Lusaka CBD, evaluating the role of taxation advisory services in influencing the behavior of SMEs, and investigating the effects of taxation on strategic business decisions. Using a mixed-methods approach, data from more than 100 SMEs were collected representing various sectors. The findings indicated that 79.2% of the SMEs were aware of their tax obligations, while only 16.7% showed deep understanding of multiple tax responsibilities. Regression results showed that the model explained 83.35% variation in compliance levels, $R^2 = 0.8335$; $F = 292.84$, $p < 0.0000$. It was observed that tax filing frequency significantly enhanced compliance, $\beta = 0.73$, $p < 0.01$, while tax awareness alone did not have a significant impact, $\beta = -0.16$, $p = 0.127$. Findings further showed that although 54.2% of SMEs attended tax advisory sessions, only 41.7% found them helpful, while 70.8% received no continuous guidance. Ordinary least squares regression showed that the quality of advisory significantly and positively influenced compliance, $\beta = 0.24$, $p = 0.012$. On strategic business decisions, 58.3% reported negative taxation effects on expansion and reinvestment, while 68% adjusted prices and 55% altered profit allocation. The study concludes that Zambia's taxation system is highly influential in strategic and compliance behavior for SMEs, and this calls for improved advisory services, simplification of compliance systems, and tax incentives targeting the SME sector to promote growth and sustainability.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Taxation remains a crucial tool for mobilizing national revenue, as well as promoting economic stability. In Zambia, the Zambia Revenue Authority is the organization responsible for the assessment, collection, and accounting of various taxes, including Value Added Tax, Corporate Income Tax, and Turnover Tax, levied in support of government programs. Regardless of such objectives, the system's complexity, high compliance costs, and frequent policy shifts have raised concerns about its impact on SMEs—the most active economic segment of the country. According to the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprise Development (2022), SMEs represent over 70% of employment and 88% of business activities in Zambia. However, most of them remain informal because of administrative challenges and perceived tax burdens.

The Zambian tax environment has, over the years, gone through a number of reforms designed to enhance equity and compliance, including e-filing and presumptive tax systems. SMEs nonetheless face procedural inefficiencies, limited advisory support, and knowledge gaps. Complex regulations have been said to deter investment, diminish profitability, and slow down formalization (Mwila, 2020; ZRA, 2021). Tax burdens also limit SMEs in expanding or reinvesting, hence influencing long-term strategic decisions. Therefore, understanding how taxation shapes SME business behavior and decision-making is relevant to the design of policies balancing revenue needs with private sector growth.

1.2 Problem Description

Although taxation is indispensable for national development, many SMEs perceive Zambia's tax system to be unfair and a burden. High tax rates, inadequate education, and bureaucratic inefficiencies diminish compliance and deter registration. In Lusaka CBD, where SME concentration is highest, such challenges have an immediate effect on price, recruitment, and investment decisions. Though previous research has examined compliance, few studies have related taxation policies to the wider decisions of business. This study, therefore, investigates the degree to which Zambia's tax system affects SME strategic and operational decisions.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective:

To assess the effects of the Zambian taxation system on business decisions among SMEs in Lusaka Central Business District.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives:

1. To examine the level of tax compliance among SMEs in Lusaka.
2. To assess the role of taxation system advisory services in shaping SME business behavior.
3. To investigate the effects of the taxation system on strategic business decisions.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the level of tax compliance among SMEs in Lusaka CBD?
2. How do tax education and advisory services influence SME tax behavior?
3. How does taxation affect SMEs' strategic and operational decisions?

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study builds on the model of tax compliance developed by Allingham and Sandmo (1972), in which compliance is treated as an expected-utility decision of taxpayers where they weigh benefits of evasion against potential penalties and detection probabilities. Recent behavioral extensions of the theory emphasize, however, that compliance is influenced also by perceived fairness, trust in authorities, and social norms (Roman et al. 2023). For the SMEs, and especially those in the informal sector, administrative burdens and complexity as a rule outweigh deterrent factors; therefore, compliance decisions are influenced not only by enforcement but also by education, advisory services, and perceived support given by tax institutions.

1.6 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the interlink of dependent variable (Taxation System) with independent variables (tax compliance, SMEs business behavior and Strategic business decisions).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

The conceptual model links taxation system characteristics (rates, procedures, enforcement) to SME decisions (investment, pricing, employment, and compliance), moderated by access to advisory services, perceived government support, and firm characteristics such as size and sector.

Independent Variable: Taxation system (rates, procedures, enforcement).

Moderators: Advisory services, perceived government support, firm size.

Dependent Variables: Business decisions (investment, pricing, employment, compliance).

1.7 Significance of the Study

This research will help policymakers, the Zambia Revenue Authority, associations for SMEs, and academia. Policymakers can use the findings to design fair and growth-oriented tax reforms. The ZRA could enhance taxpayer education and simplify the compliance systems. SME operators benefit from growing awareness of the way taxation affects their financial and strategic decisions, while scholars and researchers find empirical evidence that reinforces the literature pertaining to taxation and entrepreneurship in Zambia.

This literature review synthesizes the available material on the relationship between taxation and strategic decisions of SMEs in Zambia. It reviews a number of theoretical frameworks pertinent to taxation compliance, advisory services, and the strategic

decisions of SMEs because of the tax environment. In the Zambian context, understanding the economic importance of SMEs is essential, as they are basic elements for employment creation, innovation, and poverty alleviation (Roman et al., 2023). Despite their importance, the growth and formalization of Zambian SMEs are heavily influenced by the taxation environment, as this environment creates problems that become a barrier to development (Fjeldstad & Heggstad, as cited in OECD, 2015). The review, therefore, was conducted to get an overall understanding of: (1) the level of tax compliance among SMEs in Lusaka, (2) the use of advisory services on taxation, and (3) the effect of the taxing system on the strategic decisions made by SMEs.

2. Literature Review

2. Overview

This research will help policymakers, the Zambia Revenue Authority, associations for SMEs, and academia. Policymakers can use the findings to design fair and growth-oriented tax reforms. The ZRA could enhance taxpayer education and simplify the compliance systems. SME operators benefit from growing awareness of the way taxation affects their financial and strategic decisions, while scholars and researchers find empirical evidence that reinforces the literature pertaining to taxation and entrepreneurship in Zambia.

2.1 Tax Compliance Levels Among SMEs

Tax compliance refers to the willingness of taxpayers to comply with tax requirements as well as the ability to report their tax liabilities correctly according to the law (James & Alley, 2012). In addition, different research has identified that fear of penalties is a major driving factor toward tax compliance for SMEs (Roth et al., 2015). For example, Rohman et al. (2020) identify how social norms and taxpayer morale might ensure high levels of compliance, especially within cultures that assert societal responsibility.

Cuccia (2013), in his Brazilian research, defined tax compliance as the filing of all required tax returns on time and accurately reporting tax liability based on tax law applicable at the time the return is filed. Roth et al. (2015) reported that interviews revealed a fear for severe penalties on taxes was driving SMEs to comply with the tax law.

Rohman et al. (2020), in their studies, analyzed tax compliance as influenced by social norms and taxpayer morale across various cultures. The results indicated that SMEs in those cultures that emphasize social responsibility revealed higher compliance rates since the pressure from society to comply with tax laws contributes to good behavior.

Richardson 2015, in a cross-cultural comparison between Hong Kong and Australia, shows that Australian Small Medium Enterprises evidenced generally greater compliance than Hong Kong taxpayers. Cuccia 2013 also used a hypothetical tax scenario in experimental research studying SME taxpayers' noncompliance behavior in the US, Australia, and Singapore. The results showed that the Singaporean SME taxpayers had the highest compliance rate at almost 74 percent while Australian taxpayers had the lowest at 45 percent. The results further indicated that complete compliance was at its lowest in Australia because of the lack of sufficient tax knowledge within the country, while it was highest in Singapore because of the provision of tax knowledge to individuals before business engagement.

Andreea et al., 2015, Rawling, 2013 revealed that data collected in Bucharest depicted both compliant and non-compliant behavior amongst SMEs. They all utilized the correlation model whose results indicated both compliance and non-compliance behavior. Cuccia, 2013 reached the same conclusion and Baru, 2016 who conducted research in Germany; the results of their research were similar to those stated above. Kirchler, et al., 2013 further maintain that "no significant differences exist in terms of hypothetical tax compliance between small businesses, educated business owners or large corporates."

A meta-analysis by Murray et al. (2021) showed a consistent pattern wherein the fear of enforcement resulted in compliance but observed that intrinsic motivation was a more sustainable compliance driver in the long term for SMEs.

Cross-national comparisons show consistent patterns. For instance, Richardson, 2015 found that Australian SMEs comply more fully than those in Hong Kong. In contrast, work in vulnerable economies, such as Zimbabwe, shows that widespread corruption results in significant non-compliance, with research indicating that an overwhelming majority do not comply with tax obligations Nyamwanza et al., 2014. These findings are mirrored in studies from Malawi Banda & Malinga, 2020 and Tanzania Lubua, 2014 where noncompliance was also attributed to a lack of faith in governmental institutions.

Lubua, 2014 argues that even among the clients registered with tax authorities, a significant proportion are defaulters among the SME taxpayers. 68% of the respondents in the survey conducted in Tanzania revealed that SME taxpayers do not file their returns as stipulated by the law. In support, Atawodi, 2012 argues that many SMEs do not pay taxes hence revenues that would have otherwise been used to develop projects that would benefit SMEs are lost.

Keen et al. (2022) focused on simplifying tax procedures and argued that reducing complexity significantly increases the rates of compliance for SMEs. Their study revealed that due to the vast and complex nature of tax laws, SMEs are seldom able or willing to comply with their tax obligations. On the other hand, Chauke et al. (2023) shared a review on the role of tax incentives in enhancing compliance levels among SMEs in South Africa. They found that adequately communicated incentives can boost the level of voluntary compliance among SMEs.

Nkwe, 2013, contends that the SME taxpayer complies with all requirements by submitting their tax returns and paying tax before the due date. This was revealed in a Botswana study where it was argued that most SMEs have not received any audits by tax collectors, as they were not suspected of anything. He further contends that Botswana is recognized for its favorable tax environment which has therefore encouraged high compliance among SMEs. Adebisi and Gbegi, 2013, support high compliance levels among SMEs, arguing that "nearly all SMEs in Nigeria pay taxes regularly."

In the Zambian context, low levels of registration and payment of taxes have been documented amongst micro and small enterprises (Phiri, 2020). Other studies indicate that the majority of small traders within Lusaka conduct business informally, and

most of them do not pay monthly taxes because they are not well-equipped with financial literacy, among other bureaucratic issues (Chaponda & Chilolo, 2025). In relation to this, Kangwa & Banda (2021) stress that perceived injustice in the tax system promotes a culture of non-compliance among SMEs.

2.2 Role of Tax Advisory Services

Taxation influences several SMEs' strategic decisions, including those on investment, product pricing, formalization, and innovation. High tax rates, for instance, deter investment and growth, as various studies in developed economies have shown (Smith et al., 2025; Hanlon et al., 2017). In Africa, excessive tax burdens and complicated administrative frameworks present notable barriers that influence operational choices of SMEs (Okoye & Ezejiofor, 2021).

Taxation advisory services play a significant role in determining how SMEs view their tax obligations and, subsequently, their compliance behavior across various sectors. In this regard, the world over, tax education and awareness drives are considered as crucial tools for enhancing voluntary tax compliance. In developed countries, like the United States, the United Kingdom, and most of Europe, programs aimed at educating taxpayers on their obligations and compliance benefits are quite well-established. According to a study by Zhou et al. (2025), improved tax advisory services were found to relate directly to increased tax compliance among SMEs. The authors maintained that once SMEs receive professional tax advice, besides comprehending their obligations better, they also realize compliance benefits, hence increasing their willingness to comply with tax requirements. For example, studies by the OECD (2015) indicate that taxpayers with greater knowledge of tax laws and regulations are less likely to evade taxes. This is majorly because of their understanding of the penalties for non-compliance and fairness of the tax system. Moreover, in countries where online tax filing systems are well advanced, awareness campaigns promoting ease of filing and benefits of timely compliance lead to increased compliance rates (OECD, 2015).

In developing regions, including Africa, the effectiveness of tax awareness campaigns on compliance among SMEs has been mixed. In many African nations, such as Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, efforts to promote tax awareness among SMEs are often undermined by the large informal sector, which operates outside traditional tax system reach. In Nkosi's (2025) analysis of SMEs in South Africa, the perception of taxation as burdensome inhibits compliance was assessed. The research contends that tax advisory services must shift their focus to educational outreach and demystifying tax processes. While recognition of professional advising benefits is growing, many SMEs remain disconnected from these services due to perceived costs or lack of understanding. A study by the African Development Bank (2018) discovered that while tax awareness initiatives, such as taxpayer education programs, have had some positive effects on compliance, they are often not widespread enough to reach all SMEs, particularly those in rural or informal settings. In Kenya, for instance, the Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA) has implemented several tax education programs aimed at SMEs, but many business owners still lack basic understanding of their tax obligations. This is especially true for turnover tax, which is designed to simplify the tax process but is often misunderstood by small business owners, leading to low compliance rates (African Development Bank, 2018). A study by Makunu and Nyoni (2025) on the effectiveness of tax advisory services in Tanzania argues that although tax advisory services exist, their impact on compliance rates remains minimal due to limited engagement with informal SMEs. The authors emphasize in their analysis that informal sector businesses often lack the basic tax knowledge that formal advisory services aim to provide.

All these put Zambia in a unique position regarding how tax policy influences strategic decisions. Research has shown that bureaucratic inefficiencies, alongside constant changes in tax policy, have the effect of making SMEs unsure of the future and thus adopt conservative strategies aimed at survival in the short term rather than growth (Zimba & Kalaba, 2025; Mampofu & Sitali, 2025). Besides, the high cost of compliance forces many SMEs to operate informally, thus restricting their opportunities for finance and markets (Phiri & Simposya, 2019).

2.3 The effects of the taxation system on strategic business decisions

Consequently, this study will investigate the extent to which the tax system in Zambia impacts SMEs' strategic business decisions, mainly about investment, formalization, and pricing, filling an important gap in the literature.

Taxation is one of the most powerful instruments through which governments influence business operations and economic behavior. In the perspective of SMEs, taxes represent both a legal responsibility and a major factor influencing strategic decision-making. Whereas taxation plays an important role in public revenue, the structure, rates, and administration often shape choices that SMEs make regarding investments, pricing, employment, formalization, and innovation, among others (Hanlon, Maydew, & Saavedra, 2017). This chapter reviews how taxation affects the strategic decisions of SMEs, starting with studies outside Africa, followed by research within Africa, the SADC region, and finally Zambia.

In developed economies, for example, taxation has been found to be a significant driver of the strategic decisions of SMEs in terms of investment and expansion. In one study conducted in Canada, Smith et al. (2025) identified that high rates of corporate taxation were followed by a decline in investments of SMEs. As revealed by their study, the financial burden imposed by high taxes can make SMEs abstain from critical expansions. This concurs with Williams's study (2025), which found that the cumbersome tax systems in the EU discouraged SMEs from innovating and investing in new technologies due to the high burden of compliance.

Regarding the impact of taxation on strategic decisions within SMEs, various studies have been carried out in detail within developed economies. For instance, Hanlon et al. (2017) discovered that the high rates of corporate tax in the United Kingdom inhibit the growth of SMEs and deter them from long-term investments; rather, these companies focus on short-term survival strategies at the expense of innovation. This has also been reflected in a Taiwanese study, where it is established that excessively burdensome tax compliance obligations shift managerial time away from strategic planning and innovation and thus hinder growth (Chen, Chen, & Cheng 2020).

Evans (2018) established in Australia that SMEs have disproportionately high compliance costs compared to large corporations. These costs, derived from time and money spent on tax returns, auditing, and professional services, weigh heavily on SMEs in decisions to be either formal or informal. In the United States, Graham, Hanlon, and Shevlin (2022) found frequent changes in tax policy foster uncertainty that restrains bold investment or diversification decisions by SMEs. SMEs tend to adopt conservative financial structures to minimize tax exposure and risk.

Da Rin et al. (2019) further showed that favorable tax regimes-including lower corporate tax rates and investment allowances-encourage SME entry and growth in Europe. However, the study warned that very generous incentives without adequate accountability may indeed distort competition and resource allocation. Collectively, these studies illustrate how tax policy, compliance costs, and administrative stability impact directly upon the SME choice on expansion, financing, innovation, and market positioning.

The effect of taxation on SMEs' strategic decisions is considered an issue that has been perceived across the African continent. Okoye and Ezejiofor (2021) found that in Nigeria, multiple tax levies, complicated unclear regulations, and poor enforcement mechanisms result in reduced SME decisions to expand or formalize. Many businesses opt to remain informal to avoid the bureaucracy involved in taxation, thus limiting the avenues for formal financing and growth opportunities.

For instance, in Ghana, Abor and Quartey (2019) discovered that the low levels of tax literacy among SMEs, together with limited access to professional accounting services, negatively impact their capacity for making better decisions. This is because entrepreneurs may misunderstand certain tax requirements, consequently failing to comply with taxes and adopt inferior financial strategies. Likewise, Wanjohi and Mugambi (2020), in Kenya, documented how the relatively high rates of both turnover and income taxes limit SMEs' capacity to reinvest their profits into business development. Most of the firms put off strategic decisions like hiring or capital investment, mainly because of liquidity challenges engendered by fulfilling tax obligations.

Osei-Assibey and Bokpin (2020) argued that such effective tax reforms, including digital filing systems and simplified presumptive tax structures, enhance compliance and efficiency in decision-making. They established that transparent tax administration promotes a culture of accountability that encourages SMEs to make long-term strategic plans. Lado and Mayen (2021) also raised that harassment by revenue officers and inconsistency in tax collection in South Sudan make SMEs shy away from voluntary compliance, which in turn reduces their strategic planning for growth.

Overall, African studies demonstrate that taxation is a factor in the strategic choices of SMEs on issues of formalization, investment, and resource allocation. Excessive tax burdens, along with weak administrative frameworks, hamper long-term planning, while fairness and simplification promote compliance and sustainability.

In the SADC region, studies focus on the structural and administrative impact of taxation on the strategic behavior of SMEs. Smulders and Stiglingh (2018) report on South Africa that even with a relatively well-advanced tax administrative system, small firms incur high compliance costs, which impact strategic decisions. SMEs often outsource tax functions to consultants, increasing operational costs and decreasing funds available for strategic investments.

In the Sub-Saharan region, the SMEs operational strategies are well-moulded by taxation. Moyo and Chikadza (2025), in an investigation on the tax compliance burdens in Zimbabwe, found that the complex nature of the tax system contributes to the lack of formalizing by firms, resulting in lost access to credits and raw materials. They further mentioned that simplification of the tax system may boost its formalization.

Moemedi and Rankhumise (2019), in Botswana, concluded that delayed refunds of VAT and cumbersome systems of tax filing disrupt cash flows, which result in the SMEs having to make short-term operational decisions at the expense of their long-term growth. Similarly, Mutambara (2020), in Zimbabwe, reported that policy incoherence-especially sudden changes to VAT and PAYE rules-introduces uncertainty that discourages the SMEs from strategic investment or hiring decisions. Furthermore, Njuguna et al. (2025), in Kenya, found that frequently, high payroll taxes discouraged SMEs from hiring, thus fostering conservative business strategies toward cost-cutting rather than expansion.

Shafuda and De (2020) noted that in Namibia and Malawi, a high cost of tax compliance acts as a deterrent to formalization. Similarly, Ogunkola (2025) observed that in Nigeria, taxation is a major factor in the poor performance of SMEs; according to him, many entrepreneurs prefer to stay informal to avoid burdensome tax liabilities. However, those SMEs that adopted digital tax platforms showed improved record-keeping and better pricing strategies. These findings suggest that the tax system has a direct consequence for SMEs in their strategic decision-making at the level of cash flow management, timing of investment, and formalization.

In Zambia, an increasing number of works look into how taxation influences SME strategic behavior. Zambian SMEs face peculiar challenges emanating from bureaucratic inefficiencies in the tax administering authorities. A study by Zimba and Kalaba in 2025 has shown that the frequent changes in tax policy create uncertainty, which compels SMEs to adopt risk-averse strategies that hinder their growth. The Zambian case is similar to findings in a study by Mampofu and Sitali (2025) that emphasized the need for stability in tax legislation as a basis for effective strategic planning.

Phiri and Simposya, in their 2019 study, found the Zambian tax system to be perceived as complicated and administratively burdensome, hence the decision by many small businesses to remain informal. This decision limits access to finance and market opportunities. Similarly, Mufalo and Mulenga in 2021 found that tax compliance costs, such as hiring accountants and meeting statutory obligations, affect SMEs' pricing and investment decisions.

Chanda (2022) observed that while digital tax systems introduced by the ZRA have indeed improved compliance, they introduce other challenges, as most SMEs lack basic tax knowledge and IT capacity. Therefore, tax education can be considered another essential factor in strategic decision-making. Mwape and Mulunda (2023) further found that specific tax incentives, of which reductions in turnover tax rates are included, encourage SMEs to formalize and reinvest their profits. However, inconsistent implementation and low awareness levels reduce such incentives.

Collectively, the studies done in Zambia also highlight that SMEs view taxes as factors that determine whether to register, reinvest profits, adjust prices, or expand operations. Simplification of tax systems and raising awareness can facilitate strategic decision-making that is in tandem with national economic development aspirations.

Taxation has an impact on the strategic decisions of SMEs in various ways across the regions. Firstly, high tax rates and associated compliance costs lower retained earnings, and reinvestment is discouraged, hence affecting investment and expansion decisions of SMEs (Hanlon et al., 2017; Mwape & Mulunda, 2023). Secondly, these issues of taxation affect pricing and profit strategies because SMEs adjust prices to deal with the VAT and turnover taxes to moderate competitiveness (Mutambara, 2020).

Thirdly, tax policies engender financing strategies, where deductibility rules determine whether SMEs depend on debt or equity. Fourth, formalization and compliance strategies are strongly tax-driven; a simplified system and lower rates will boost registration, while complex procedures are a factor in discouraging registration. In addition, taxation impacts location and operational strategies, since firms might move locations to areas with more favorable tax environments. It also further has an effect on innovation and diversification strategies; for example, high tax uncertainty reduces risk-taking and innovation. Also, payroll taxes affect employment and wage strategies, resulting in SMEs adopting informal hiring practices. Overall, the literature shows that taxation has a strong influence on the behavior and strategic decisions of SMEs in Zambia. The influence of perceived unfairness and knowledge about tax on compliance and tax burdens on investment and price-setting decisions calls for focused tax policies aimed at fostering compliance but, at the same time, stimulating strategic development in the SME sector. This paper intends to contribute to the debate on the reform of tax policy to facilitate SME economic viability in Zambia as an important pillar for sustainable economic development.

3. Methodology

This section outlines the comprehensive methodology adopted in the study, detailing the research design, population, sampling techniques, data collection methods, data analysis, validity and reliability considerations, ethical issues, and limitations. This methodology is structured to ensure reproducibility of the research findings and provides a robust framework for addressing the research questions.

3.1 Research Design

In this paper, a mixed-methods research design, which included both the quantitative and qualitative approaches, is adopted. The quantitative approach involves the administration of structured questionnaires to obtain numerical data on tax compliance levels, tax advisory exposure, and the process of making business decisions. In the qualitative approach, semi-structured interviews are used to add depth to the context of the findings. The justification for adopting a mixed-methods approach is essentially related to the fact that taxation is complex in nature, and its impact on SMEs tends to be multifaceted. While quantitative methods enable generalization, qualitative methods uncover subjective perceptions and challenges of SMEs regarding the tax system (Bryman, 2016). A survey strategy is adopted because it can accomplish what is required in terms of getting information from a widely-varied SME population within a limited time frame (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2019). In order to add credibility to the results, key informant interviews are conducted with officials from the Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) and representatives from SME associations.

3.2 Target Population and Study Area

The target population includes registered SMEs in Lusaka, as defined by ZDA (2021). The study area will cover the Lusaka CBD, a locale with a high concentration of SMEs involved in various activities, among which are trade, services, transport, construction, and manufacturing. The presence of relevant institutions involved in this study, like ZRA and ZDA, adds an important context to understand the tax compliance challenges faced by SMEs.

3.3 Sampling Design

A stratified random sampling method is used to select SMEs across different sectors, ensuring the representation of different strata within the population. This study's sampling frame includes official lists of SME registrations from ZDA and the Patents and Companies Registration Agency. SMEs will be randomly selected in each sector to minimize biases that might occur during sampling. For the qualitative part, key informants such as tax consultants, leaders of associations of SMEs, and ZRA officials will be identified through purposive sampling, since their insight is important in gaining a more comprehensive understanding of tax compliance issues.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The sample size is determined using Yamane's formula, 1967, the estimated target population of around 5,000 registered SMEs in the CBD. With a confidence level of 95% and margin of error of 5%, the sample size determined is around 370 SMEs. However, the study will eventually target a sample size of 120 SMEs along with 12 to 15 key informants for qualitative interviews due to resource constraints.

3.5 Data Collection Methods and Instruments

Data will be obtained from primary and secondary sources. In the process of collecting primary data, structured questionnaires will be administered to SME owners, which capture demographic information, compliance behaviors, exposure to tax education, and perceptions about taxation's influence on decision-making. The questionnaires will be divided into four sections: demographic characteristics, tax compliance behavior, exposure to tax advisory services, and perceived effects of taxation on business

decisions, with responses gathered through both open-ended and Likert-scale questions. In qualitative data collection, semi-structured interviews will be facilitated with key informants through the use of an interview guide to ensure consistency in the discussed topics while leaving room for further probing. Secondary data will be collected from various documents such as annual reports by ZRA, policy papers, statistical bulletins, and academic literature in order to contextualize primary data and increase comprehensiveness of the analysis.

3.6 Data Analysis

Quantitative data is coded and analyzed using the SPSS and STATA software, where responses are summarized using descriptive statistics in the form of means, frequencies, and percentages. Inferential statistics-correlation and regression analysis, in particular-are used to test the hypothesized relationships among tax compliance, education, and strategic decisions by the SMEs. Regression analysis, in particular, tests the influence of taxation on important investment, financing, and expansion decisions.

4. Findings

4.0 Overview

This chapter provides the results obtained from analyzing primary data on the impact of the taxation system on the business decisions of SMEs in the Lusaka CBD, Zambia. These findings are targeted at understanding the level of compliance of SMEs with the payment of taxes, the impact of tax advisory services on SME behavior, and the general impact of taxation on business decisions. Each finding has been supplemented by relevant figures and tables for summarizing and placing in context the data.

4.1 Background Characteristics of the Respondents

4.1.1 Demographic Information

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are critical in setting the context within which tax compliance and decision-making are made by SMEs. This section therefore elaborates on age, gender, education, type of business, number of employees, years of operation, registration status, year established, monthly revenue, and average monthly profits.

4.1.2 Age of Respondents

The age of the respondents is another important demographic factor that helps in understanding the characteristics of the sample population. This section shall present the distribution of age among the respondents of the study. Clearly, age will affect perception, behavior, and response to survey questions, hence the need for the analysis and reporting of the age profile of the sample.

Table 1 Age of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	20–30 years	36	30.0
	31–40 years	56	46.7
	Above 40 years	28	23.3
	Total	120	100.0

Table 1 highlights that the majority of respondents (46.7%) fell within the age bracket of 31–40 years, with 30% aged 20–30 years. These findings indicate that SME ownership in Lusaka’s CBD is largely among younger adults. This demographic advantage may facilitate tech adoption in tax operations, although it also suggests a relative lack of experience in navigating complex tax regulations.

4.1.3 Gender of Respondents

Understanding the gender composition of the respondents is important in assessing the possible gender-based differences in response. This section therefore gives an analysis of the gender distribution of the respondents who took part in the study, highlighting the proportion of males and females in the sample.

Figure 1. Gender of Respondents

Figure 1 illustrates a gender disparity, with 58.3% of respondents being male and 41.7% female. This finding resonates with national entrepreneurial patterns where gender inequalities exist. Such disparities may thwart equitable business participation and underscore the need for targeted support mechanisms for female entrepreneurs.

4.1.4 Level of Education

Education is one of the important demographic variables that may define perception, awareness, and understanding of the research topic among respondents. This question looks into the educational attainment of the respondents, reporting the highest level of education completed by the respondents. Analyzing the educational profile of the sample will help to contextualize the findings and understand how education might have an impact on the outcomes in this study.

Figure 2. Level of Education of Respondents

Source: Field Data

Approximately 49.1% of the respondents have attained tertiary education, contributing to their understanding of financial and taxation concepts. Increased literacy among SME owners may correlate positively with tax compliance.

4.1.5 Type of Business

The nature of the business the respondents are engaged in is an important factor to understand their experiences, challenges, and perspectives. This section develops an analysis of the type of businesses presented in the study, categorizing them by industry or sector. Looking at the types of businesses helps in observing any patterns, commonalities, and differences in response, hence giving valuable context to help interpret the research findings.

Table 2. Type of business

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Type of Business	Sole Proprietorships	55	45.7%
	Partnership	30	25.0%
	Private Limited Company	20	16.7%
	Public Limited Company	5	4.2%
	Non-Profit Organization	5	4.2%
	Cooperatives	5	4.2%
	Total	120	100.0%

Source: Field data

Table 2 reveals that 45.7% of respondents operate sole proprietorships, indicating the prevalence of micro-enterprises within the CBD. These businesses often grapple with tax compliance due to limited resources and accounting capabilities, necessitating tailored tax policies and advisory support.

4.1.6 Number of Employees

The size of an organization is normally determined by the number of employees and can thus affect its operational structure, resources, and strategic decision-making processes. This section indicates the distribution of respondents based on the number of employees in their respective organizations. The following analysis about the size is important to understand the representativeness of the sample and assess how organizational size might impact the study's outcomes.

Figure 3. Number of Employees

Source: Field Data

The analysis indicates that 41.7% of SMEs employ fewer than five workers, confirming the dominance of micro-enterprises in Lusaka’s economy. Limited staffing may hinder their financial capacity to engage in comprehensive tax management practices.

4.2 Tax Compliance Behavior

ax compliance behaviour refers to the extent to which taxpayers comply with their tax obligations, including filing correct and timely tax returns and paying the proper amount of tax. A clear understanding of the tax compliance behavior of the respondents will help identify trends, challenges, and factors that influence compliance. This section examines tax compliance behaviour of the respondents by providing insights into the adherence to tax laws and regulations.

4.2.1 Awareness of Tax Obligations

Awareness of tax obligations is perhaps one of the prime influencers of tax compliance. This section looks at the level of awareness by the respondents concerning their obligations, knowledge of tax laws, filing requirements, and payment deadlines. Understanding awareness levels can be helpful in the identification of potential gaps in taxpayer education and areas where interventions may be necessary to improve compliance.

Figure 4. Awareness of Tax Obligations

Figure 4 indicates that 79.2% of SMEs are aware of their tax obligations. However, the existence of a substantial segment that remains unaware (20.8%) highlights gaps in outreach and education. Awareness of tax obligations is a precursor to compliance, but as the data suggests, awareness does not necessarily equate to actual compliance.

4.2.2 Regularity in Filing Tax Returns

The regularity of filing by taxpayers is one of the most important indicators of tax compliance. This section discusses how often and consistently the respondents file their tax returns on time, outlining various patterns in compliance and non-compliance. An assessment based on regularity of filing can outline the challenges that might have affected taxpayers while also pinpointing areas for possible improvement in tax administration and support.

Table 2 Regularity in Filing Tax Returns

Frequency of Filing	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Monthly	28	23.3
Quarterly	40	33.3
Annually	32	26.7
Never	20	16.7
Total	120	100

Source: Field data

Table 3 depicts that the highest percentage of SMEs (33.3%) file tax returns quarterly, yet a significant number (16.7%) have never filed a tax return. This gap may be attributed to financial constraints and the administrative burden of frequent filings.

4.2.3 Challenges in Tax Compliance

Various challenges impede tax compliance, ranging from complexity of tax laws to resource constraints. This section identifies and examines the key challenges encountered by respondents in meeting their tax obligations, shedding light on obstacles that impede compliance and areas where support or reforms might be needed.

Table 4 . Challenges in Tax Compliance

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of knowledge	72	60.0
High tax rates	64	53.3
Complex procedures	85	70.8
Poor communication from ZRA	50	41.7
Other (e.g., digital access issues)	25	20.8

Source: Field Data

Table 5 presents the challenges SMEs face regarding tax compliance. Complexity of tax procedures (mean = 4.5) emerges as a considerable barrier, corroborating recent literature that emphasizes practical tax compliance limitations faced by SMEs.

Table 5: Severity of Challenges (1–5 Scale Mean Scores):

Challenge	Mean Score
Lack of knowledge	3.9
High tax rates	4.2
Complex procedures	4.5
Poor communication	3.8
Other challenges	3.6

Source: Field data

4.2.4 Test statistic on levels of compliance

Effective taxation requires not only compliance but also access to advisory services that support the navigation of increasingly complex tax laws and regulations. The section provides information on the types of taxation system advisory services used by the respondents, such as tax consulting, audit support, and training. Its analysis may help pinpoint the gaps in support and windows of opportunity to better the education and compliance outcomes of taxpayers. The paper discusses the role and impact of taxation advisory services. This was helpful for some SMEs; however, significant gaps in outreach remain evident.

Table 6 levels of compliance

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	120
Model	57.6498929	2	28.8249465	F(2, 117)	=	292.84
Residual	11.5167737	117	.098433964	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.8335
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8306
Total	69.1666667	119	.581232493	Root MSE	=	.31374

easyofcompliance	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
taxawareness	-.1570307	.102193	-1.54	0.127	-.3594186 .0453572
fillingfrequencies	.726267	.0408494	17.78	0.000	.6453669 .807167
_cons	.554247	.0901963	6.14	0.000	.3756178 .7328761

Source: Field Data

Regression: model explains 83.35% of variation in compliance ($R^2 = 0.8335$; $F = 292.84$; $p < 0.0000$). ordinary least square revealed that increased filing frequencies significantly enhance compliance, yet tax awareness shows no direct correlation.

4.3 Taxation System Advisory Services

Effective taxation requires not only compliance but also access to advisory services that support the navigation of increasingly complex tax laws and regulations. The section provides information on the types of taxation system advisory services used by the respondents, such as tax consulting, audit support, and training. Its analysis may help pinpoint the gaps in support and windows of opportunity to better the education and compliance outcomes of taxpayers. The paper discusses the role and impact of taxation advisory services. This was helpful for some SMEs; however, significant gaps in outreach remain evident.

4.3.1 Attendance at Advisory Service Sessions

The outcome of tax advisory services solely depends on how helpful they are perceived in attempting to satisfy taxpayers' needs and compliance difficulties. This section assesses respondents' perception of the usefulness of the tax advisory services on aspects such as clarity, relevance, and influence on compliance behavior. The strengths and weaknesses within current services are determined through analysis, thereby informing likely potential improvements that can be made in order to support taxpayers more effectively.

Table 7 Attendance at Advisory Service Sessions

Response	Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	Have attended one or more tax advisory sessions.	65	54.2%
No	Have never attended any tax advisory sessions.	55	45.8%
Total		120	100%

Source: Field data

Table 7 shows that 54.2% of SMEs have attended at least one tax advisory session, denoting partial program success while indicating that outreach efforts need to be intensified.

4.3.2 Helpfulness of Tax Advisory Services

The effectiveness of tax advisory services depends on their perceived helpfulness in addressing taxpayers’ needs and resolving compliance challenges. This section evaluates respondents’ perceptions of the usefulness of tax advisory services, including aspects such as clarity of information, relevance, and impact on compliance behavior. The analysis identifies strengths and weaknesses of current services, informing potential improvements to support taxpayers more effectively.

Table 8 Helpfulness of Tax Advisory Service Sessions

Response	Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Very helpful	Significantly improved tax compliance and understanding.	20	16.7%
Helpful	Moderately improved knowledge and compliance	30	25.0%
Not helpful	Did not lead to noticeable improvement	10	8.3%
Never attended	Did not participate in any sessions	75	62.5%
Total		120	100.0%

Source: Field data

Among those who attended, only 41.7% found the sessions helpful, emphasizing the necessity for more targeted and substantive educational content.

4.3.3 Ongoing Tax Guidance

Ongoing tax guidance is essential for taxpayers to stay update with changes in tax laws, regulations, and procedures. This section examines respondents’ access to and preferences for ongoing tax guidance, including sources of information, frequency of updates, and perceived adequacy of support. The findings inform on the current state of support mechanisms and potential gaps in keeping taxpayers informed and compliant.

Table 9 Receipt of Ongoing Tax Guidance

Response	Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	Currently receive tax support or guidance from ZRA or other sources	35	29.2%
No	Do not receive any tax-related guidance.	85	70.8%
Total		120	100%

Source: Field data

The substantial number of SMEs (70.8%) not receiving ongoing tax guidance indicates a critical gap in continuous support, consistent with literature suggesting that such support is essential for improving tax compliance among SMEs.

4.3.4 Test statistic

To assess the impact and reach of tax education initiatives, this section presents statistical analysis of respondents’ attendance at tax education sessions, workshops, or training programs. The test statistics examine patterns, frequencies, and correlations, providing insights into the coverage and potential effects of tax education on compliance and taxpayer behaviour.

Table 10 Regression analysis

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. reg easyofcompliance helpfulness qualityrate attendededu

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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	120
Model	53.025262	3	17.6750873	F(3, 116)	=	127.02
Residual	16.1414047	116	.139150041	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	69.1666667	119	.581232493	R-squared	=	0.7666
				Adj R-squared	=	0.7606
				Root MSE	=	.37303

easyofcomp-e	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
helpfulness	.1062339	.1035439	1.03	0.307	-.0988478 .3113157
qualityrate	.2380341	.0931721	2.55	0.012	.053495 .4225732
attendededu	.4796659	.1085488	4.42	0.000	.2646713 .6946605
_cons	-.1528347	.1092053	-1.40	0.164	-.0634602 .3691295

The regression model highlighted attendance at tax education events strongly increases ease of compliance ($\beta = 0.48, p = 0.0$) while quality of advisory services positively influences compliance (coef = 0.24, $p = 0.012$). The output is shown in the figure below

4.4 Effect of Taxation System on Strategic Business Decisions

This section explores how taxation influences SMEs' strategic decisions, outlining the broader implications for business operations and growth potential.

4.4.1 Impact on Expansion

The taxation system plays a significant role in shaping business strategies, influencing investment, pricing, and an expansion plans. This section examines respondents' perception of how tax policies and regulations affect their decision making, highlighting key challenges and opportunities. The analysis provides insights into how tax considerations drive business choices and competitiveness.

Table 11 Effect of Taxation on Business Expansion

Response	Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	Taxation has negatively influenced expansion decisions	70	58.3%
No	Expansion decisions have not been affected by taxation	30	25.0%
Not sure	Uncertain whether taxation has affected expansion plans	20	16.7%
Total		120	100.0%

Source: Field data

As delineated in Table 8, a significant majority (58.3%) of SMEs report that the tax system negatively affects their expansion plans, demonstrating a clear link between tax policy and business growth.

4.4.2 Influence of Taxation on Pricing and Hiring Strategies

Taxation can significantly impact business decisions on pricing and human resource management. This section explores how respondents' businesses adjust their pricing strategies and hiring practices in response to tax rates, incentives, and compliance costs. The analysis reveals the extent to which tax considerations shape these critical business decisions.

Table 12 . Effect of Tax on Pricing Strategies

Response	Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	Tax issues affect one or more strategic areas	75	62.5%
No	No effect on operational or strategic decisions	25	20.8%
Not sure	Uncertain about the impact of tax	20	16.7%
Total		120	100%

Source: Field data

Evidence from the findings suggests that many SMEs have adjusted prices upward (68%) to compensate for tax burdens. This upward pressure on prices remains a prime concern, especially for SMEs operating in already tight profit margins.

4.4.3 Long-term Planning

Tax policy can significantly shape a company's long-term strategic direction, influencing decisions on investments, expansions, and resource allocation. This section analyzes respondents' perceptions of how tax policies impact their long-term planning, including the effects of tax incentives, stability, and uncertainty on business sustainability and growth.

Table 13. Influence of Tax Policy on Long-term Decisions

Response	Interpretation	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Not at all	Tax has no significant impact on planning	15	12.5%
Slightly	Minimal consideration in long-term strategies	20	16.7%
Moderately	Some influence on planning and budgeting	35	29.2%
Strongly	Major factor in decision-making	30	25.0%
Very strongly	Central to strategic and financial planning	20	16.7%
Total		120	100%

Source: Field data

Over half of SMEs (56%) perceive tax policy as a strong influencing factor in their long-term planning, suggesting that more predictable tax policies could stimulate investment and growth.

4.4.4 Ordinary Least Square output

This section presents the results, examining the impact of specific policy variables on tax compliance levels using regression analysis. The results provide insights into which policy levers are most effective in enhancing compliance, informing evidence-based policy adjustments.

Table 14 Regression analysis

. reg easyofcompliance expansioneffect policyinfluence						
Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	120
Model	57.2065124	2	28.6032562	F(2, 117)	=	279.81
Residual	11.9601542	117	.102223541	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.8271
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8241
Total	69.1666667	119	.581232493	Root MSE	=	.31972

easyofcompliance	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
expansioneffect	-.0154242	.0767228	-0.20	0.841	-.1673697	.1365214
policyinfluence	.5616967	.0467025	12.03	0.000	.4692049	.6541884
_cons	.3290488	.0799105	4.12	0.000	.1707903	.4873074

Source: Field Data

Test for significance reviewed $R^2 = 0.8271$; it showed that the model explained 82.7% policy measures positively influence compliance ($\beta = 0.56$, $p < 0.001$).

In summary, the findings indicate that while a significant proportion of SMEs in Lusaka’s CBD are aware of their tax obligations, many face systemic barriers to compliance. High tax rates, complex procedures, and limited access to advisory services significantly influence their capacity to fulfill tax obligations. Moreover, the findings suggest that the tax system directly impacts strategic business decisions, notably expansion, pricing, and long-term planning.

These observations call for urgent reform in Zambia’s tax framework, emphasizing the need for streamlined processes, improved communication, and enhanced support for SMEs. Simplifying compliance burdens and extending education to SMEs through targeted outreach can create a more conducive environment for business growth, ultimately contributing to the country’s economic development. Addressing these gaps can expand the tax base while promoting a more dynamic and resilient SME sector.

4.5. Discussion of Findings

This section interprets and discusses the research findings, with reference to the study objectives, the literature reviewed, and theoretical frameworks. The discussion integrates quantitative results, as shown in tables and charts, with qualitative interpretation to provide a holistic understanding of how taxation affects SMEs in Lusaka central business district.

The findings of this study illuminate the intricate relationship between taxation and the operational dynamics of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Lusaka central business district. The research reveals that while awareness of tax obligations among SME owners is relatively high, actual compliance is thwarted by numerous systemic challenges, including complex procedures and high tax rates. This inconsistency in compliance behavior underscores the need for effective communication and educational initiatives by the Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA), which currently faces limitations in outreach and effectiveness.

4.5.1. Interpretation of Demographic Findings

The demographic profile revealed that SME ownership in Lusaka central business district (CBD) is dominated by men (58.3%) though women constitute a significant 41.7%. This finding is consistent with World Bank (2022) data which shows that women’s participation in SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa has been steadily rising, albeit with persistent barriers such as limited access to finance and training. The relatively balanced gender representation suggests that taxation policies must consider the diversity of SME operators, especially since women-owned enterprises are more likely to be in vulnerable, informal sectors.

4.5.2. Business Profile and Strategic Implications

Sole proprietorships dominate (50%), with limited employees (5–10 for 41.7%) and moderate revenue (ZMW 5,001–10,000 for 37.5%) (Tables 1–5). These demographics indicate SMEs have limited capacity to absorb tax burdens, consistent with Akinleye (2017). Longer-operating SMEs show better formalization and financial management (Musungu, 2018).

4.5.3. Awareness and Knowledge of Tax Obligations

The results show that 79.2% of SME owners were aware of their tax obligations, while 20.8% were not. This finding demonstrates a moderate level of tax literacy, but also a notable knowledge gap. Such gaps are problematic as awareness is a critical determinant of compliance. The Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) has introduced taxpayer education initiatives, yet the fact that more than one-third of SMEs lack basic awareness suggests limitations in outreach.

These results confirm findings by Atawodi and Ojeka (2012), who noted that lack of knowledge is among the leading causes of non-compliance among SMEs in developing economies. They also align with Kirchler's (2007) "slippery slope framework," which highlights that knowledge and trust are as important as enforcement in ensuring voluntary compliance. These findings also align with Cuccia (2013) who used a hypothetical tax scenario in their experimental study to investigate the SME taxpayers' noncompliance behaviour in the US, Australia and Singapore. Their findings suggested that complete compliance was lowest in Australia due to lack of tax knowledge within the country and was the highest in Singapore because of the tax knowledge given to the individuals before they embark on a business.

4.5.4. Compliance Behavior

The findings revealed that most SMEs in Lusaka central business district (CBD) (79.2%) are aware of their tax obligations, yet actual compliance remains inconsistent, with 16.7% never filing tax returns and a majority finding compliance procedures difficult. This aligns with the conceptual framework discussed in Chapter Two, particularly the Allingham and Sandmo (1972) model of tax compliance, which posits that taxpayers' decisions depend not only on the probability of detection and penalty severity but also on their perceived administrative burden and fairness of the system.

SMEs in this study reported complex tax procedures (70.8%), high tax rates (53.3%), and limited knowledge (60%) as major obstacles — consistent with findings from Lubua (2014) in Tanzania and Nyamwanza et al. (2014) in Zimbabwe, who also observed that compliance costs and system complexity discourage SMEs from fulfilling their tax obligations. The results confirm that non-compliance in Lusaka central business district (CBD) is more structural than attitudinal — rooted in administrative inefficiencies rather than deliberate evasion.

Moreover, the findings support OECD (2015) and Roman et al. (2023), who emphasized that compliance decisions are shaped by perceived fairness, simplicity, and government trust. SMEs who view taxation as unfair or excessively complex are less motivated to comply voluntarily. This is also consistent with Zambian micro-level studies (Chaponda & Chilolo, 2025) that attribute low compliance to limited awareness and perceived inequity in tax enforcement.

The results therefore suggest that voluntary compliance could improve through simplification of procedures, fair enforcement, and enhanced digital access rather than through punitive enforcement. This reinforces the behavioral approach to tax compliance, which emphasizes trust and transparency as stronger motivators than fear of penalties.

4.5.5 Taxation Advisory Services

The study found that just over half (54.2%) of SMEs had attended tax education or advisory sessions, and 41.7% of those rated them as helpful. However, 70.8% reported not receiving continuous guidance. These findings underscore the partial success and significant limitations of Zambia's taxpayer education initiatives.

This outcome resonates with the arguments of Fauziati et al. (2016), Kasippilai and Jabbar (2013), and Saad et al. (2013), who found that adequate tax knowledge enhances compliance by improving understanding of obligations and reducing unintentional errors. In contrast, Bird (2014) and Harris (2012) cautioned that knowledge alone may not automatically lead to compliance unless taxpayers perceive the system as fair and beneficial. The present study's findings fall between these perspectives: tax education increases awareness and confidence but is insufficient in isolation to ensure full compliance.

The finding that only 20.8% rated education quality as good or excellent mirrors OECD (2015) observations that Zambia's taxpayer education, while extensive in outreach, often lacks depth and measurable behavioral outcomes. Furthermore, the absence of continuous guidance (reported by 70.8% of SMEs) reflects the gap identified by Chaponda & Chilolo (2025) — that sporadic, generic campaigns fail to meet the practical needs of SMEs who require ongoing, sector-specific advisory support.

From a theoretical standpoint, this supports behavioral and institutional models of compliance, which posit that sustainable compliance depends on consistent communication, legitimacy of institutions, and perceived reciprocity — taxpayers must see tangible benefits from their contributions.

In summary, while ZRA's education efforts have raised awareness, their limited frequency and practical application weaken their effectiveness. To achieve meaningful results, tax education must transition from periodic information dissemination to continuous, targeted advisory engagement.

4.5.6 Taxation effects on SMEs' Strategic Decisions

The third objective examined how taxation influences SME strategic decisions. Decisions most sighted include expansion, pricing, hiring, and formalization. The results showed that 58.3% of SMEs reported that taxation negatively affected expansion plans, 68% adjusted prices in response to tax burdens, and 39% limited hiring. These findings demonstrate that taxation is not merely an administrative concern but a strategic determinant of business sustainability and growth.

The evidence aligns strongly with the findings of Hanlon, Maydew, and Saavedra (2017), who argued that high tax rates discourage investment and innovation, and with Graham et al. (2022), who found that policy uncertainty undermines long-term business planning. Similarly, Okoye and Ezejiofor (2021) in Nigeria and Wanjohi and Mugambi (2020) in Kenya established that high and unpredictable tax burdens constrain expansion and formalization — outcomes mirrored in the Lusaka central business district (CBD) SME context.

The observed adjustments in pricing and employment also correspond with Mutambara (2020) and Mufalo and Mulenga (2021), who demonstrated that SMEs often pass tax costs to consumers and reduce staff to maintain profitability. Thus, the present study validates regional evidence that taxation directly shapes firm-level strategy and operational flexibility.

Notably, 50% of SMEs in Lusaka central business district (CBD) indicated that the tax system influenced their decision to formalize. This aligns with Mwanza (2019), who found that many firms register primarily to avoid penalties rather than to access benefits. This confirms that Zambia's formalization process remains compliance-driven rather than incentive-driven. Osei-Assibey and Bokpin (2020) emphasized that sustainable formalization arises when governments pair enforcement with tangible benefits such as credit access or simplified tax regimes — a principle highly relevant to Zambia.

The results further affirm Da Rin, Di Giacomo, and Sembenelli (2019), who noted that favorable tax regimes can encourage SME entry and growth, provided they are predictable and transparent. However, in the current Zambian context, frequent policy changes and administrative burdens appear to deter rather than attract formal participation.

In summary, taxation significantly shapes strategic decision-making among SMEs in Lusaka central business district (CBD) by influencing investment, pricing, and employment choices. Excessive tax burdens and complexity erode profitability and discourage reinvestment, while fair and simplified systems can promote compliance and growth.

4.6.1 Effects of Taxation on Profitability and Operations

The findings show that 55% of respondents believe taxation reduces profitability, and 61% report that it constrains reinvestment. This provides strong evidence that the current tax system undermines SME capacity for growth. Profitability is already constrained by limited market size, access to finance, and inflation; taxation adds another layer of financial strain.

These results resonate with studies in Nigeria and Kenya (Atawodi & Ojeka, 2012; Musamali & Tarus, 2013), where high taxes similarly discouraged SME expansion. They also align with the resource-based view of the firm, which posits that retained earnings are essential for growth and innovation. By reducing available resources, taxation reduces SMEs' ability to invest in technology, new markets, or additional employees.

4.6.2 Taxation and Strategic Business Decisions

Taxation's broader impact on business decisions is evident that findings illustrate that 68.3% of SMEs adjusted pricing strategies, 45.8% experienced reduced consumer demand, 39.2% delayed recruitment, and 26.7% reduced their workforce due to tax pressures. These results reveal taxation as not just a compliance issue but also a strategic factor shaping competitiveness and sustainability.

This finding aligns with contingency theory, which suggests that external environmental factors such as taxation influence strategic decisions. Slemrod (2007) also emphasizes that taxation affects firm behavior beyond compliance, influencing investment and employment.

Interestingly, 34.1% of respondents indicated that taxation had no impact on employment. This suggests heterogeneity among SMEs, with some firms able to absorb tax burdens due to higher revenues or sector-specific advantages. This heterogeneity supports Schumpeter's (1934) argument that resilience and innovation are unevenly distributed across enterprises.

4.6.3 Policy Reforms Desired by SMEs

The reform preferences showed overwhelming support for simplification, digitalization, fairer enforcement, and incentives for formalization. Simplification was ranked the top priority, reflecting a consensus that compliance costs are too high. Digitalization was also highly favored, consistent with Okunogbe and Santoro (2021), who found that digital platforms significantly improve compliance in developing economies.

The demand for incentives to encourage formalization aligns with Lewis's (1954) dual economy theory, which stresses the need to transition informal enterprises into the formal sector. Linking compliance with tangible benefits such as access to finance could transform the taxation system from a burden into an enabler of SME growth.

However, the study is not without limitations. While it provides valuable insights within the Lusaka context, the findings may not be universally applicable across different regions of Zambia or other developing economies. Further research is necessary to explore these dynamics in varied contexts, aiding in a more comprehensive understanding of taxation's influence on SMEs.

5 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of the Study

This study set out to assess the effects of the taxation system on business decisions among SMEs in Lusaka, Zambia. The research was motivated by the recognition that SMEs form the backbone of Zambia's economy, yet they continue to face significant challenges in complying with taxation policies, which in turn shape their strategic and operational decisions.

The objectives of the study were fourfold: (1) to evaluate SMEs' awareness and knowledge of tax obligations, (2) to determine the challenges faced in complying with taxation policies, (3) to examine the impact of taxation on SMEs' strategic decisions such as pricing, employment, and expansion, and (4) to identify potential policy reforms that could enhance tax compliance and SME growth.

A mixed-methods design was employed, with primary data collected through structured questionnaires distributed to SME owners and managers across Lusaka. The findings revealed that while the majority of SMEs are aware of their tax obligations, the complexity of tax regulations, high tax rates, and inadequate tax education significantly constrain their compliance capacity.

Quantitative data showed that 68.3% of respondents reported adjusting pricing due to taxation, 45.8% reduced demand for their services, and over 39.2% delayed recruitment plans because of the tax burden. A significant proportion of SMEs (55%)

highlighted taxation as a major factor reducing profitability and reinvestment opportunities. The qualitative insights confirmed these patterns, revealing frustration with ZRA's communication strategies, limited access to advisory services, and perceptions of unfair enforcement.

5.2 Conclusions

The study concludes that taxation exerts a strong influence on SME operations and strategic choices in Lusaka central Business District. Although awareness of taxation obligations is relatively high, effective compliance remains hindered by systemic and structural barriers. SMEs perceive the current tax system as burdensome, costly, and not sufficiently tailored to their size or sectoral realities.

The research further concludes that taxation significantly shapes SMEs' expansion, employment, and pricing strategies. Many SMEs delay or scale down growth plans because of the financial strain imposed by taxes, while others adjust their pricing structures to remain competitive, which sometimes reduces profitability. Importantly, the lack of consistent tax education and advisory services perpetuates misinformation and discourages voluntary compliance.

The study affirms that tax policy reforms, if properly targeted, could significantly enhance compliance and strengthen SMEs' role in Zambia's economic development. Simplification of tax processes, digitalization of services, and the introduction of size-based graduated taxation stand out as potential measures with broad SME support.

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1 Policy Recommendations

- **Simplify Taxation Procedures:** The Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) should streamline filing and payment procedures, reducing bureaucratic complexity and making the system more SME-friendly.
- **Graduated Taxation:** Introduce a tiered taxation model where rates are proportionate to business size and revenue, ensuring that micro and small enterprises are not unfairly burdened.
- **Enhanced Tax Education and Advisory Services:** Regular tax awareness programs and advisory clinics should be conducted to equip SME owners with knowledge on compliance and available incentives.
- **Digitalization of Tax Systems:** Strengthening e-filing and digital payment platforms would reduce administrative costs, curb corruption risks, and increase efficiency.
- **Fair Enforcement Mechanisms:** Enforcement should be firm yet fair, with penalties proportional to the offense, accompanied by education rather than purely punitive approaches.
- **Sector-Specific Approaches:** Policies should recognize differences in sectors (e.g., retail, manufacturing, services) and design tax regimes accordingly to encourage compliance.
- **Incentives for Formalization:** Provide tax-based incentives such as access to affordable loans or government tenders to businesses that transition from the informal to the formal sector.

5.3.2 Recommendations for SMEs

- **Capacity Building:** SME owners should proactively seek tax training opportunities to build internal capacity in financial management and compliance.
- **Adoption of Digital Tools:** Businesses should leverage accounting software and e-tax platforms to minimize errors and delays in filing.
- **Collective Advocacy:** SMEs should collaborate through associations and chambers of commerce to lobby for favorable tax reforms and share compliance best practices.

5.3.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies should expand the geographical scope to other provinces of Zambia to allow comparative analysis across rural and urban SMEs. Moreover, longitudinal research would provide insights into how evolving tax policies influence SME performance over time. Finally, a deeper exploration of sector-specific taxation effects (e.g., agriculture vs. technology) would enrich the evidence base for policy design.

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